

Operando Acoustic Spectroscopy for Optimizing Gas Evolution In Hydrogen Evolution Reaction and the Oxygen Evolution Reaction Processes

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The use of earth-abundant materials for novel electrodes for solar-driven electrolysis will play a significant role in the future production of hydrogen as a green energy source. The choice of electrolyte will play a major role in how efficient and stable future photoelectrochemical cells (PEC) operate. A new approach to determining PEC efficiency using broadband acoustic resonance dissolution spectroscopy (BARDS) is investigated to analyze the real-time production of hydrogen and oxygen at platinum electrodes in different electrolyte solutions. The parameters investigated include concentration of electrolyte, surface area of the electrode, and the potential applied to the cell.

Herein, the suitability of neutral buffer as an electrolyte on a par with either acid or basic electrolytes is shown. This finding allows for the potential design of solar to hydrogen electrolyzers which can operate under mild, neutral, and stable conditions using earth-abundant materials for hydrogen production. It is also shown how BARDS can readily visualize and track gas evolution in real-time and in situ in an open system without the need for gas collection. It is anticipated that the technique can be utilized in the future evaluation of newly developed electrode materials in terms of efficiency, stability, and life span.

1. Introduction

The hydrogen economy is a term used to describe an energy pathway with hydrogen at its core.^[1] It is an effort to reform the current energy system, which relies almost exclusively on the burning of fossil fuels and emission of harmful pollutants (such as CO and CO₂). The green hydrogen economy aims to combine the cleanliness and sustainability of hydrogen gas

(H₂) as an energy source, with the efficiency of fuel cells to obtain electricity.^[1] Currently, most hydrogen is produced from steam methane reforming, accounting for 48% of all hydrogen gas produced today, and involves the catalytic cracking of fossil hydrocarbons into carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and H₂ at temperatures between 700 and 900 °C.^[2] Hydrogen produced using this process is called gray (conventional) hydrogen.^[3] Despite the apparent cleanliness of hydrogen, it is the mode of production which determines its sustainability. Electrochemical decomposition of water requires a potential input of more than 1.23 V which is approximately equal to the energy of radiation (1,000 nm). Therefore, visible light shining on the right electrochemical system should decompose water without the use of a potentiostat.^[4]

Kang et al. (2020) have proven a critically important aspect of the ability to obtain operando quantitative measurement of the actual gas evolution during hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and oxygen evolution reaction (OER) inside a standard hydrogen electrode cell and inside the electrolyte itself.^[5] This is achieved using broadband acoustic resonance dissolution spectroscopy (BARDS) analysis as opposed to extrapolation from a GC or mass flow controller/meter methods in a closed electrochemical cell. Kang et al. also accurately determined both HER or OER gas volume evolution in real time accounting for gas solubility and capturable gas volume. The ability to determine the on-set of gas evolution at electrodes and to characterize bubble evolution and growth is critical to the development of new sustainable electrodes and efficient photoelectrochemical cells (PEC). BARDS analysis is capable of elucidating these parameters in an open system. Fitzpatrick et al. (2012) have described the principles of BARDS analysis.^[6] Previously, Grimmer et al. have used gas

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chromatography to quantify the amount of H₂ gas in a mixture for two different electrochemical cell designs. The first design included the supply of two carrier gases, H₂ to the counter electrode, and an inert carrier gas N₂ to the test electrode used to transport the H₂ to the detector. The design is limited to gas mixtures that are free from O₂ or other oxidants/reducible constituents. An overpotential is applied to the test electrode where hydrogen is oxidized (release of electrons). The protons that are formed travel across the membrane to the counter electrode. The reverse reaction takes place, and then the resulting electrons are analyzed according to Faraday's law. The second design used electrodes placed into an acidic liquid electrolyte. The cell consisted of gas channels, diffusion layers, and an active layer within its structure. The main advantages for this design setup are the ability to detect at lower quantities or levels of H₂ gas and the elimination for the need for H₂ gas to be supplied to the counter electrode as a carrier gas. Therefore, the design and correct selective methods of H₂ quantification are required for the purpose of developing future technologies.^[7] These examples show the involved complexity of characterizing H₂ production and the need for simpler approaches to ascertain cell efficiency. The most widely used method is GC and direct analysis. The main drawbacks from these methods include impurities in the flow controller, or noise and poor time resolution.^[8] In this article, BARDS is used as a more reliable tool for analyzing and visualizing the production of gas in situ within the electrochemical cell in real time without the need for a closed system with carrier gases. Sherman et al. focused on the OER analysis in electro and PEC using fluorine-doped tin oxide electrodes. The GC analysis of O₂ requires the removal of any presence of atmospheric O₂ gas. This problem is overcome by using isotopic labeled water, which guarantees that the O₂ comes from the electrolyte. Another method is the phosphorescence quenching method used in closed cells. This method has low Faradaic efficiencies, and in photoelectrochemical analysis, the light can create noise and obstruct the O₂ concentration measurement.^[8] Currently, there are many techniques used to assess bubble detachment, which is one of the three stages of water electrolysis.^[9] Atom force microscopy (AFM) is a useful technique for analyzing surface features by inserting a probe to vibrate the surface and obtain nanoscale bubble size results. The main drawback of this technique is a

change to the surface from the impact of the mechanical probe, causing changes to the size of the bubbles formed from altered nucleation sites.^[10] High-frequency impedance bubble monitoring is an in situ characterizing method that lacks sensitivity to detect the smaller bubbles produced in solution.^[11] There are a few techniques that can aid in the release of bubbles from the surface, namely: acoustic field, magnetic field, and supergravity field.^[12] The newest method for bubble characterization in an electrochemical cell is a fiber optic sensor. It is a highly precise detection method that gives information on bubble detachment, bubble growth rate, and intake/output ratio.^[13]

There are new ways of producing stable HER and OER using non-noble metal nanomaterials.^[14–16] Efforts have been made in producing cheap, efficient electrodes from new materials that mitigate the need for costly metals.^[17–22] HER mechanisms have been examined extensively in electrochemical literature, e.g., the descriptor most used for the electrolysis reaction is the metal–H_{ad} bond energy.^[23–27] Strmcnik et al. identified two other descriptors; the proton source and the presence of surface spectators to better assess hydrogen electrocatalysis. They also used Ni(OH)₂ to modify the metal, which helped stabilize the OH[–] in aqueous electrolyte. It was verified that the difference between the acidic and alkaline electrolyte is due to the hydrogen evolving from a different proton donor. Their study found there are many questions left unanswered in relation to intermediates, products, and surface activity at the HER which may be answered with new in situ experimental tools such as BARDS.^[28] Thermodynamic volcano curves are used to compare different metals and different metal complexes. The plots express the relationship between the metal hydrogen bonding to the rate of HER. These plots do not explain why activity in acidic solutions is several orders of magnitude greater than alkaline solutions for the majority of metal catalysts.^[29]

Table 1 provides a comparison of the advantages and disadvantages of various gas/bubble detection methods available. BARDS shows significant advantages in its ability to detect low levels of gas both on the electrode or in the electrolyte in situ without the requirement to collect gas from the cell. A BARDS unit can be acquired at the lower end of the cost for an average bench-top instrument.

Table 1. Advantages and disadvantages of a range of commonly used analytical methods.		
Analytical method	Advantages	Disadvantages
BARDS	Fast, no need for a closed system, H ₂ detection limit, <i>pico</i> -Molar. It can detect gas on the electrodes or undissolved in the electrolyte.	Stirring required to induce acoustic resonance
Fiber optic sensor	Precise real-time monitoring of bubble formation; good spatial resolution	Detection limit in the micrometer scale (≈80 μm)
High-frequency impedance spectroscopy	Versatile way of characterizing bubble behavior; real-time quantitative analysis	Lacks the sensitivity to detect the production of smaller bubbles
AFM	Gives useful information about the surface chemistry and Nano bubbles	Can cause damage to the electrode surface, which alters bubble formation
gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy (GC-MS)	Fully quantitative; able to assess mixtures of gases	Complex and expensive setup. Difficult to operate and requires a closed system, requires gas collection

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials

The following materials in Table 2 were used for the study.

2.2. Instrumentation

A Temma power supply was used to provide the potential. A modified BARDS spectrometer was used for acoustic analysis of the electrolysis experiments. A Jenway 1000 magnetic stirrer hot plate was used with a fixed stirring rate of approximately 200 rpm. A Metrohm 654 pH meter was used to adjust the pH of the solutions. Figure 1A shows a typical BARDS spectrum with the application of current (0.5 V) at 30 s in potassium hydroxide (0.5 m). The resulting resonance curve is used to acquire data points, as shown in Figure 1B. This data acquisition is used throughout the results section to capture the effects of changing parameters such as applied potential, concentration of electrolyte, and surface area. The experimental set-up is shown in (C)

2.3. Methodology

The principles and applications for BARDS are given by Fitzpatrick et al.^[6] The change in gas volume within solution during electrolysis causes a decrease in the resonant frequency of the cell which is detected using a microphone. The cell is induced to resonate by allowing a magnetic follower to gently tap the inner wall in solution. A power supply is used which sends a direct potential through platinum wires in the electrolyte solution. H₂ is formed at the cathode and O₂ at the anode for total water splitting. A typical spectrum is shown in Figure 1. The potential is applied at 30 s to the platinum electrodes. Hydrogen and oxygen evolution reactions (HER, OER) happen at the cathode and anode, respectively. The frequency decreases with an increase in compressibility of the electrolyte due to a corresponding increase in gas volume. A steady-state plateau is reached at approximately 200 s, and the potential is switched off. This plateau signifies an equilibrium between gas evolution at the electrodes in the electrolyte and gas leaving the electrolyte at the surface. The frequency returns to its initial steady state in the absence of potential with no gas evolution taking place at approximately

Table 2. Materials and chemicals used in this study.		
Chemical name	Supplier	Batch/lot number
98% sulfuric acid	AnalaR	K26944855
Potassium phosphate	Sigma-Aldrich	MKCC7897
Potassium hydroxide pellets	Emsure	B1556433820
Potassium phosphate	Sigma-Aldrich	SLBG7384V
Potassium chloride	Sigma-Aldrich	BCBV0117
Hydrochloric acid	Merck	K42753614 137
Sodium hydroxide	Sigma Aldrich	STBJ9514
Platinum wire	Merck	327,492–2.6G

Figure 1. a) An unprocessed BARDS frequency/time spectra for a full cell reaction using platinum working and counter electrodes in 0.5 m KOH and a potential of 2.5 V. Note: the potentiostat was switched ON at 30 s and OFF at 220 s. b) A processed BARDS spectra showing acquired data points and highlighting the important parts of the spectrogram. Note: the potential is applied and removed at the same time points as in a). c) A top down view of the experimental full cell set-up for BARDS analysis. The potentiostat is viewed face on.

500s time frame due to all nondissolved gases exiting the solution.

The potassium phosphate buffer (PBS pH = 7.0) was prepared using a mixture of mono (4.4 g) and dibasic phosphate (3.4 g) in 50 mL volumetric flask. Initial experiments were carried out to ascertain changes in frequency, compressibility, and gas evolution in solution during electrolysis in basic solution. Two platinum wires were connected to a DC supply and placed in potassium hydroxide solution at a depth of 10 mm. The negative electrode (cathode) and positive electrode (anode) have a diameter of 1 mm. The total surface area of the electrodes in contact with the solvent solution is approximately 0.33 cm² at 1 cm depth. The glass vessel (100 mL cell) contains 50 mL of an aqueous potassium hydroxide solution. Two 1 mm diameter Pt electrodes

were used and placed into solution at a depth of 1 cm, giving a total surface area of $\approx 0.33 \text{ cm}^2$. The distance between the two Pt wires was kept at 2.0 cm. The minimum amount of current required to split water was $\approx 1.9 \text{ V}$. Similarly, for Kang et al.^[5] a response was induced at $\approx 1.9 \text{ V}$. Li et al. have stated that it is possible to split water at 1.23 V theoretically but in practice a voltage of $\approx 1.8 \text{ V}$ is required to overcome the activation barrier of the reaction.^[30]

A 2 cm long magnetic follower with a pivot ring was used and placed off center in the glass cell. It made a good contact with the glass when stirring at approximately 200 rpm. All electrolytes were prepared using deionized water. The resonant frequency of the cell/vessel remains constant ($\approx 8.7 \text{ kHz}$) for a fixed volume of solution.

The changes to acoustic resonance from the glass caused by contact with the magnetic follower are detected by the microphone and measured over time to generate a spectrum. Two identical glass vessels are used for the half-cell reaction, and the microphone is mounted over the vessels. Where applicable to half-cell measurements, a U-shaped salt bridge is used which is filled with different concentrations of potassium chloride (KCL). The surface area of the electrodes is $\approx 0.33 \text{ cm}^2$ for both the cathode and anode under investigation. The cathode electrode is submerged in one of the glass vessels and the anode in the other. The volume line frequency is monitored for the first 30 s before the voltage is applied. The potential is then applied for 190 s to the system causing the formation of gas bubbles on the surface of the platinum electrodes. Finally, after this period of time, the potential is switched off and a return to steady state frequency is observed before the 800 s time point. All experiments are run in duplicate, and the results are then plotted.

3. Results and Discussion

The following results outline how the electrolysis of water can be tracked with ease in full and half-cells where multiple variables are adjusted, including potential, electrolyte, concentration, and surface area. The contribution of all of these variables is important to ascertain for the optimization of photo-electrochemical cells. It is challenging to measure gases in a closed system, however, the following results have been determined in an open system in real time and in situ.

3.1. Effect of Applied Potential on Gas Evolution

The data in **Figure 2** shows the frequency changes associated with the electrolysis of water in a basic solution depending on the change in voltage applied to the Pt electrodes. Applied potential is the first parameter under investigation using BARDS. The potential applied to the cell during electrolysis is one of the key parameters studied using the BARDS apparatus. Gas evolution was evaluated during total water splitting at various potentials in the range of 2.0–4.0 V in 0.5 M KOH solution.

Figure 2. a) BARDS frequency curves between 2.0 and 2.5 V in 0.5 m potassium hydroxide at 0.33 cm^2 surface area, b) corresponding gas volume plot. c) Plot of peak gas volume v applied potential.

Figure 2a shows the resulting BARDS frequency spectrum obtained. Each profile represents a duplicate experiment. A reduction in the acoustic frequency, consistent with the production of gas altering the compressibility of the solution, was noted at all potentials except for 2.0 and 2.1 V where the overpotential is probably not sufficient to produce electrolysis. The BARDS profiles in Figure 2b show that there is little gas production in the potential range of 2.0–2.2 V. A small increase in potential to 2.25 V (green profile) shows a significant increase in gas production. In the

potential range of 2.25–4.0 V there is a high rate of gas evolution in the initial phase (30–41 s) when the potentials are first applied. The rate reduces to a more modest level at these higher potentials after 41 s and increases again at 126 s at 2.3 V and at 83 s for the highest potentials. There is no further rate change noted before the potential is switched off, and the gas volume decreases at a similar rate as the bubbles migrate to the surface and exit the electrolyte. The data then tails off to zero probably as a result of residual gas leaving the cell more slowly, e.g., gas bubble retention on the electrodes.

Figure 2c shows the linear relationship between the applied potential and the peak gas volume produced at steady state for potentials between 2.25 and 3.0 V. A threshold is reached above this potential at which no additional gas production is observed, as shown in Figure 2b, for 4.0 V. This is possibly due to the surface area being saturated with bubble evolution as shown in the Figure S1, Supporting Information. Bubbles can be seen to saturate the length of the electrode. The slope of Figure 2c can be used to semiquantitatively predict the gas volume if the cycle time and applied potential are known.

3.2. The Effect of Electrolyte pH on Gas Evolution

Another important parameter is the chosen electrolyte and its pH used during electrolysis to determine effect of gas evolution. Figure 3a–e shows the output BARDS curves acquired at different electrolyte concentrations, namely KOH, PBS, and H₂SO₄. All experiments were carried out at a potential of 2.3 V. In general, the higher the electrolyte concentration the lower the frequency deflection in the BARDS response which correlates to an increasing gas volume produced.

Figure 3a shows the frequency changes associated with an increase in concentration of the KOH. There is a decrease in frequency at the lowest concentration of 0.25 m KOH to 8.5 kHz after which point there is no further change for ≈270 s until the potential is switched off. The frequency plateau indicates a steady state production of gas at a potential of 2.3 V at this concentration. A further increase in concentration to 0.3 and 0.4 m results in a similar frequency profile plot for both concentrations. There is an initial fast rate of production followed by a more modest rate until the frequency minima is reached just above 6 kHz at which point the potential is switched off. Note, each experiment is cycled in duplicate before the concentration is changed. The rate of gas loss thereafter is equivalent to the rate of production when the potential is first applied, given the symmetric shape of the curves. The peak gas volume changes significantly when the concentration is increased further to 0.5 m and above with little significant change thereafter with higher concentration. A rapid increase in gas volume is observed in Figure 3b when the concentration is increased to 0.5 m KOH (red profile). This is followed by a slowdown in the rate after 50 s. A third rate change (increase) is evident at 150 s. The potential is removed after 200 s, and the gas volume returns to steady state. An approximate 24-fold increase in gas volume was measured from 5.0×10^{-1} to 1.2×10^{-2} mL, when experiments were conducted with

electrolyte concentrations of 0.25 and 0.5 m, respectively at a concentration of 1.5 m as indicated by the staircase/stepwise production of gas. Although interesting, it would be unwise to propose a mechanism for a stepwise bubble growth based on a duplicate measurement with large spread.

Overall, peak gas volume most likely lies within a small window of concentration between 0.25 m and 0.5 m. At the highest concentrations, the residual gas remains elevated in the cell and takes a long time to decrease. Residual gas is not dissolved gas which is available to contribute to the increased compressibility of the electrolyte, which is observed between 300 and 750 s. This is an indication residual gas bubbles are populating available surface areas in the cell during the experiments at higher concentrations. These results indicate a threshold value (0.4 m KOH) has been surpassed in terms of concentration to facilitate optimum gas production.

Figure 3c represents the same set of experimental conditions as Figure 3a, except the only change is the electrolyte from KOH to PBS. There is an insignificant amount of gas produced at a concentration of 0.25 m PBS as indicated by the frequency change in Figure 3a and gas volume in Figure 3b.

Increasing the concentration to 0.5 and 1.0 m PBS leads to a modest increase in peak gas volume of 2.0×10^{-3} mL. However, there is a significant increase in peak gas volume when the concentration is increased to 1.25 m and again to 1.5 m with a peak of 12×10^{-3} mL. The data suggest a threshold concentration has been exceeded to facilitate electrolysis in PBS. This observation is similar to that for KOH in Figure 3b.

Finally, Figure 3e shows the BARDS response for electrolysis in H₂SO₄ electrolytes. This electrolyte produced significant gas volume. Peak gas volume had not been reached by the standardized cut off point for the potential (220 s). This may be expected for the electrolysis of a polyprotic species. Figure 3f shows the gas volume is slightly above 0.12×10^{-3} mL for both 0.25 and 0.5 m. The gas volume is similar to both the 0.5 m and 1 m solutions of KOH (Figure 3b) and 1.25 m PBS. Figure 3g,h shows the data for electrolysis in HCl. A peak gas volume of 19.2×10^{-3} mL is achieved with a potential of 2.3 V and a concentration of 0.5 m, 37% higher than all the electrolytes tested thus far.

A further increase in potential to 3.0 V results in a modest increase in gas volume. The increase in the potential range 2.3–3.0 V has a 4% increased efficiency at 2.0×10^{-3} mL compared to lower voltages. There is also a significant increase in the current density at higher potential, Figure 4d.

In Figure 4a–d, the current density reaches a maximum at the “ON” point at 30s and decreases over time. In Figure 4a, the red profile (0.5 m KOH) reaches a zero current density at approximately 180 s, and for the black profile (0.25 m KOH), it reaches at approximately 40 s. This may be caused by the reduction in the conductivity of the electrolyte solution by the presence of gas bubbles adhering to the electrodes for longer at lower concentrations.^[30]

Figure 5a shows a composite of results for five of the best electrolyte solutions which are presented to compare frequency profiles and gas volume data at a fixed concentration of 0.5 m

Figure 3. a) Time/frequency plot of electrolysis with a concentration gradient for KOH. b) Corresponding gas volume plot, c) time/frequency plot of electrolysis with a concentration gradient for PBS. d) Corresponding gas volume plot, e) concentration gradient for H₂SO₄, and f) corresponding gas volume plot. g) Time/frequency plot of electrolysis in HCl with varying concentrations, h) corresponding gas volume plots. (Note: H₂SO₄ 0.5 m, 0.25 m, and 0.125 m; measured pH is 0.5, 0.98, and 0.68, respectively, the KOH 0.5 m and 0.25 m pH is 13.2 and 12.79, respectively, HCl 1 m and 0.5 m; pH is 0.13, and 0.40, respectively).

Figure 4. a) Current density values during the electrolysis for KOH, b) current density values during the electrolysis for PBS, c) current density values during the electrolysis for H₂SO₄, and d) current density measured during electrolysis in HCl.

and a potential of 2.3 V. Figure 5b represents the corresponding gas volume data which shows a ranking of electrolyte performance under these conditions for electrolysis.

The data in Figure 5b indicate that a standard concentration for each electrolyte will result in significantly different levels of electrolysis at a fixed potential. However, the concentration for each electrolyte can be adjusted to achieve optimum gas production as indicated in Figure 5c.

Three of the electrolytes, other than HCl, show similar optimum gas output by also adjusting the electrolyte concentration HCl out performs the other electrolytes significantly. Theoretically, H₂SO₄ is the same acidity as HCl due to its diprotic nature. Overall, these results are significant in that they show a neutral electrolyte gives a comparable output, which can be employed for use with novel electrode made from earth-abundant materials, particularly when they may be less stable in more acidic or basic conditions. Note it is possible to further improve the production of gas using saturated K-phosphate solutions at 80 °C and 100 °C.^[31]

These temperatures were found to be optimal to minimize the losses originating from mass- transport (diffusion, convection, and migration) at the neutral pH when a diaphragm is used to keep the gases separated. Their work demonstrates that the concentrated buffer solutions are a promising electrolyte for water electrolysis under neutral pH conditions. It is highly unlikely that electrolyzers in the future will run at these temperatures due to the energy input required. However, surfaces designed for solar collection can reach relatively high temperatures to further facilitate gas production.

It is a step change in the measurement of the efficiencies of electrolytic cells that BARDS can follow the life cycle of gas evolution at the electrode until it reaches the surface of the electrolyte. These measurements are in real time and in situ compared to off-line sniffing techniques which rely on capture once gases have left the solution.^[32]

The data in **Figure 6** shows the frequency changes associated with the electrolysis of water in a basic solution depending on the surface area of the electrodes. Note that the applied voltage is 2.5 V, which is 0.2 V higher than previous experiments. The effect of increasing potential is known from Figure 2a. This was employed to boost gas production for the lowest surface area. In Figure 6a, the black profile (total surface area = 0.17 cm²) initially has a modest change in frequency after the potential is applied at the 30 s "ON" point. Unusually, the frequency is observed to increase gradually while the potential is maintained until it reaches a steady state at 150 s. This may indicate that the rate of loss at the surface may be equal to or slightly greater than the rate of gas evolution. The available small surface area of the electrodes is very close to the surface of the solution, hence any gas produced will exit quickly due to its high buoyancy.

The gas has less distance to travel to exit the solution than gas produced lower down on a higher surface area. A further increase in surface area leads to a very significant decrease in frequency to minima of 3 kHz. Figure 6b shows the corresponding gas volume plots which show that the smallest surface area produces a relatively small amount of gas. In Figure 6c, there is also an initial spike in current density at 30 s. Then the current density steadily

Figure 5. a) Comparison of electrolysis (Pt electrodes, 0.33 cm² total surface area) in 0.5 m KOH, 0.5 m PBS, and 0.5 m H₂SO₄ under standard conditions of concentration, potential, and surface area. b) Corresponding gas volume plots measured by BARDS. c) Composite threshold gas volume plot overlay of optimum gas evolution under standard conditions except for electrolyte concentration.

drops to essentially zero at 150s time point even though the potential is still being applied. This may be due to the electrodes becoming saturated with insulating bubbles and the production of gas is retarded.

This is also indicated by the gradual frequency rise in Figure 6A where the compressibility for the black profile starts to increase rather than decrease at 40 s until the 220 s OFF point. It is evident that a larger surface area facilitates higher gas production in the cell.

3.3. BARDS Analysis of HER and OER Half-Cells

In an effort to compare gas evolution of hydrogen and oxygen separately, an approach was developed to generate these gases individually in half-cells. Therefore, a salt bridge arrangement was required to facilitate this objective. Figure 7A,B assesses the effect of a change in concentration of KCL within the salt bridge on electrolysis for a half-cell set-up. A comparison of gas evolution at the anode and the cathode will be established.

Figure 7a shows that as the concentration of KCL increases, there is a corresponding decrease in frequency for the cathode part of the half-cell. Figure 7b shows the peak gas volume increasing with increase of KCL concentration. As shown in Figure 7c, when the polarity of the system is switched, that there is no frequency change when the KCL concentration in the salt bridge is 0.1 m. However, the frequency decreases thereafter as the salt bridge concentration increases at 1.5 m, 2.0 m, 2.5 m, and 3.0 m concentrations. This is also the case in Figure 7d with the O₂ gas volume increasing with salt bridge concentration.

It is important to note that ten times more hydrogen is detected compared to oxygen in Figure 7b–d instead of the theoretical 2:1 ratio at the highest KCL concentration. However, the ratio is as expected when the KCL concentration is 1 m. This indicates that oxygen is going undetected at higher KCL concentrations. It is known that at high pH oxygen bubbles will grow to two orders of magnitude greater in size than hydrogen bubbles before they detach from a narrow electrode. The inverse is true at low pH. The electrolyte in the half-cells is KOH therefore the pH is high with larger oxygen bubbles which are more likely to exit at the surface than smaller bubbles. An equivalent volume of smaller bubbles also has a greater surface area which may allow for a higher dissolved oxygen concentration.

Figure 7e shows the corresponding current density profile for three measurements (1–3 m KCl) of salt bridge concentration. The initial current density is observed to increase more rapidly with increasing salt bridge concentration. The current density is then seen to decrease at higher concentrations to a steady state at a constant potential (4 V). The resistance is therefore increasing correspondingly. The current density decreases to zero for the lowest salt bridge concentration of 1.0 m. This may indicate a depletion of ions to facilitate electrolysis or possibly due to the added resistance from the presence of gas bubbles adhering to the electrodes. Sodium sulfate was also investigated as a potential electrolyte for the salt bridge but it was found to be less suitable than KCl. Ionic strength has also been considered as a contributory factor but was found to be not significant (further details can be found in the Supporting Information). The choice of a salt bridge instead of an electrolyzer was made in order to isolate the contribution of each gas

Figure 6. a) Frequency changes associated with the electrolysis of water (2.5 V) in 0.5 m KOH as a function of electrode surface area. b) Corresponding gas volume determined from BARDS, and c) current density profile overlay. d) Relationship between gas volume produced and the surface area of the electrode.

to the compressibility of the electrolyte in the half-cells. This would not be possible in a full cell set-up.

It is possible, using an approach used by Kang et al., (refer to Supporting Information) to plot the total amount of gas produced, V_B (which is the total gas volume and is calculated from V_t and k_{el}) during the electrolysis experiment against the salt bridge concentration. Figure 7f shows a linear relationship between salt bridge concentration and log of the total amount of hydrogen gas produced during the electrolysis (V_B) ($r^2 = 0.97$). This indicates that the salt bridge concentration is critical in a half-cell set-up and small fluctuations in concentration will affect the level of electrolysis significantly. The theoretically expected amount of gas produced during the period of applied potential is shown in Table 3.

The value of k_{el} is determined from the first-order return of the gas volume to zero. The theoretical volume by the Faraday equation (V_F) has previously shown that V_B is ≈ 12 times lower than V_F (Faraday equation); this is assuming complete faradaic efficiency where just a single electron electrochemical process for hydrogen occurs. In Table S1, Supporting Information, we show a similar response using KOH as the electrolyte. The V_F is ≈ 10 times greater than V_B for 2 M KCL and 0.5 M concentration of KOH. The ratio between the observed (V_B) and expected values (V_F) varies between 0.0343 and 0.2387.

This investigation used BARDS analysis to comprehensively assess, in operando and in situ, the contributions of multiple parameters required for electrolysis to take place at Pt electrodes. These included applied potential, type of electrolyte, concentration of electrolyte, surface area of electrodes a salt bridge electrolyte concentration.

A linear relationship ($r^2 = 0.99$) was observed between applied potential and peak gas volume for electrolysis in KOH electrolyte until a threshold is reached at $\approx 4V$. There is a lower threshold of 0.25 m KOH at which no electrolysis is observed at a potential of 2.3 V. However, there is a significant increase in electrolysis observed by increasing the KOH concentration from 0.30 m to an upper threshold of 0.5 m, which indicates a narrow window of concentration for optimum electrolysis conditions.

Electrolysis proved to be equally efficient using PBS buffer as the electrolyte but it required higher concentrations. However, even greater efficiencies are expected at higher operating temperatures. This would be amenable for PEC where surface temperatures can reach 65 °C.

Peak gas volume was found to be marginally better using H₂SO₄ as the electrolyte at half the concentration of KOH. However, H₂SO₄ is diprotic which facilitates electrolysis more favorably. HCl electrolyte proved to be optimum for electrolysis

Figure 7. a) BARDs analysis of H₂ evolution at the cathode with different concentrations of KCl in the salt bridge, b) the corresponding gas volume plot. c) BARDs analysis of O₂ evolution with different concentrations of KCl in the salt bridge and d) the corresponding gas volume plot. e) The main current density for the half-cell experiments, f) VB for the change in concentration of potassium chloride in the salt bridge. (Note: using a 0.5 m KOH solution, Pt surface area of 0.33 cm² and 4 V was used throughout these experiments because of the increased resistance due to the salt bridge).

Conc KCl	V _t [mL s]	Kel[s ⁻¹] [×10 ⁻³]	V _B [mL] [×10 ⁻³]	Q _t [C cm ⁻²]	V _F [mL] [×10 ⁻²]	V _B /V _F
1 m	0.040	5.70	2.27	0.09	1.0	0.21
1.5 m	0.079	4.10	3.24	0.76	9.5	0.03
2 m	0.155	48.0	7.43	1.14	11.8	0.06
2.5 m	0.169	98.0	16.56	1.52	21.3	0.08
3 m	0.337	63.0	21.21	1.90	23.7	0.09

at a potential of 3.0 V and concentration of 1.0 m before a threshold is reached. Optimum electrolysis was determined for all the parameters investigated based on observed boundary conditions of potential and concentration and gas volume thresholds, as presented in Figure 5C.

Furthermore, exploratory experiments using half-cell apparatus allowed for the detection of oxygen and hydrogen separately. However, there was a discrepancy found between the theoretical and experimental gas volume expected between the two gases.

The real-time dynamic tracking and quantification of the gas evolution in water splitting directly within the electrolyte in full or half-cells has been achieved, following on from the work of Kang et al. This has allowed for the following conclusions to be established.

4. Conclusion

The BARDS analysis technique is applied to comprehensively assess—in operando and in situ—the contributions of multiple parameters for solid surface electrolysis. Platinum metal is employed as the electrode material, in the form of full-cell Pt rods, for standard experiments and as large area solid Pt surfaces to form preferential half-cells in order to assess surface area effects on the gas bubble surface dynamics specifically. We successfully show real-time BARDS dynamic tracking and quantification of the gas evolution directly within the electrolyte in full or half-cells, incorporating an assessment of the elimination rate of bubbles at the surface. A key finding has been the suitability of a neutral buffer as an electrolyte for the electrolysis process, which we show to be equally effective as strong acids or base electrolytes. This observation opens up the possibility of using less aggressive electrolyte concentrations for both the anode and cathode half-cell reactions, simplifying the redox process and reducing the predicted complexity and cost. The extension of the BARDS technique to assess electrolytic gas evolution for half-reactions at electrolyte/electrode interfaces of solid materials provides a significant advantage in assessing the main contributing parameters for optimum surface performance. This will help to maximize the rate of production of hydrogen fuel across different surface areas and topologies. This offers an alternative, cost-effective, noninvasive intervention pathway to real-time, in situ, direct monitoring and visualization of gas evolution during electrolyte/electrode solid surface electrolysis for green hydrogen fuel production. This will ensure optimization of the process by monitoring key parameters, such as the rate of hydrogen production, the rate and area distribution of hydrogen bubble release, and adhesion. This can be achieved without the need to rely on costly and complex systems with high-end detection instrumentation. These systems provide little or no information regarding solvent compressibility, complex rates of change in gas evolution or any direct assessment of cause and effect in order to rectify and maintain an optimum process. Therefore, they cannot provide a reduced risk of maintenance requirement and expensive downtime periods, nor provide the potential for increased hydrogen fuel production efficiency and reduced system complexity and cost.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare the following competing financial interest(s): the authors wish to state that Dr. Dara Fitzpatrick is a director of BARDS Acoustic Science Labs Ltd.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: broadband acoustic resonance dissolution spectroscopy · electrochemistry · hydrogen · hydrogen evolution reaction · oxygen evolution reaction · spectroscopy · water splitting

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